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MOTIVATION AS A BOOSTER FOR LANGUAGE LEARNING

In nowadays Ukraine, more and more universities that teaching foreign students offer them studies in English medium. That is why we need to reconsider the way of teaching Russian language for non native speakers in circumstances of bilingual environment.

However, so to understand which methodology one needs to use in order to succeed, first we need to understand the motivation of the learner. The scientists have been holding considerable interest how motivation influences the learner of the language and yet this issue needs to be revised.

It is worth mentioning that students of non-linguistic universities are primarily focused on their specialty disciplines. Besides, some have a technical mindset, while others find it difficult to learn foreign languages and other humanitarian disciplines. Thus, many of them shelve it as an unimportant discipline. However, after only few months they realize that knowing Russian language is not only a need but rather a necessity. As everyday they have to endure a routine life in a Russian speaking community, where a simple trip to the store can turn into a challenge. Right on that point starts to shape the motivation for language learning.

Rogova G.V. in her work "Foreign Language Teaching Methodology" has made the main focus on the variety of motivations. Therefore she brought out next types – communicative motivation, linguistic-cognitive motivation and instrumental motivation.

- communicative motivation – implies interest in the subject from the point of view of expressing their own opinions in foreign language teaching lessons;
- linguistic-cognitive motivation – is a positive attitude of students to the linguistic matter itself, to the study of the basic properties of linguistic signs;
- instrumental motivation – motivation arising from the positive attitude of students to certain types of work [1:9-17].

While studying motivation as one of the crucial component of foreign language learning, Rogova G.V. defines motivation as "the side of the subjective world of the student, which is determined by his own motivations and addictions, conscious of his needs" [1:6].

As for teachers part, we need to create a comfortable and full-fledged environment for a student to develop and boost his motivation in language learning. That is why we would like to highlight the importance of further studying of

instrumental motivation. Since it is the teacher's task to choose appropriate types of work for students that will motivate them the most.

References:

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The aim of this thesis to analyze the importance of motivation within language learners as a key way to acquire better language skills.

Key words: motivation, Russian language, learning languages.